

THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN PROVIDING EMPLOYMENT AND CREATING NEW JOBS.

SULAYMONOV AKMALXON
ASADULLAYEVICH

Master student
Associate Professor **I.I.Soliyev**

Annotation: *The article examines the problems of job creation and employment in employment and the role of small business and private entrepreneurship in the employment and job creation of the population.*

Keywords. *Government, Employment, Labor, Active Population Reforms, Programs.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, about 60% of the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan is directed to the social sphere. Formation of a new system of health care and social protection of citizens, increasing the level of medical services and rehabilitation of the disabled, targeted state support of the most vulnerable and needy strata of society, providing them with specialized, high-tech medical care Complex work is underway to further improve the quality of delivery and provision of social services.

As a result of the implementation of state social programs, the health of the population has significantly improved over the past period, maternal mortality has decreased by 3.2 times, child mortality by 3.4 times, life expectancy has increased from 66 to 74 years, women and in the middle to 76 years.

In the current period of action strategy for socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, labor market policy is based on the development of methods and forms of state regulation and new forms of management. The State Employment Service is an integral part of the implementation of state policy in the labor market, defining the main directions and objectives of its implementation. The state employment service is aimed at achieving

positive social and economic benefits in the labor market. This will, on the one hand, create conditions for the allocation of a large number of employed people to the State Employment Fund in accordance with the norm, and on the other hand, reduce the number of unemployed pensioners and create conditions for active directions. This, in turn, increases the quality of their employment.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Employment", Presidential Decrees, Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers and a number of normative and legal acts on the effective use of labor in ensuring employment have been adopted. positive changes are taking place in this area. However, at the regional level, a number of scientific and practical issues related to the involvement of labor resources in productive work, the creation of new jobs, the efficient use of labor remain relevant.

Employment means, first of all, that the economically active population has an income-generating activity in accordance with the legislation. According to Article 2 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Employment", employment is related to the satisfaction of personal and social needs of citizens, which does not contradict the legislation , is an activity that brings them wages (labor income).

"The need for job creation and employment in 2020 is 1335.3 thousand people. The number of employed is 388531 people.

According to preliminary data, the permanent population of the republic as of April 1, 2020 amounted to 34036.8 thousand people, and in 2020 increased by 131.6 thousand people or 0.4%. In particular, the urban population is 17,183.7 thousand people, the rural population is 16,853.1 thousand people, which is 50.5% of the total urban population and 49.5% of the rural population.

On the basis of the program in Samarkand region, 45,114 or 12.9% increase in 39,952 jobs and new jobs were created.

In the current conditions of socio-economic development associated with the implementation of economic reforms in our country, the priority is to develop and implement the goals and objectives of employment policy in line with the conditions of economic development. Employment of the population in various forms and

directions of labor activity related to ensuring a modern quality of life, creating conditions for the development of human capital and ensuring a relatively high level of division of labor includes It is impossible to ensure social stability, further advance the path of economic reforms and ensure a modern labor market without ensuring reasonable employment of the population. At the same time, taking into account the specifics of our national economy, it is important to develop targeted programs based on the promotion of active employment, which will re-create a multi-sectoral economy with an anti-crisis employment policy. Accelerating the process of development should be closely linked with the reform of structural changes in the economy and the overall strategy for the development of labor resources.

METHOD AND TECHNOLOGY

To study the role and importance of the state budget and other state trust funds in the financing of social protection and to expand and strengthen the sources of funding for social support measures in the context of limited state resources is the goal of the graduate qualifying work. To achieve these goals, the following tasks have been identified:

- study the budgetary mechanism of social protection and analyze the role and importance of the state budget;
- Analysis of the specifics of the implementation of mechanisms to ensure the targeting of social protection in the regions;
- Explain the role and importance of pensions in social protection;
- To study the practice of using extra-budgetary funds of the Pension Fund in social protection;
- Development of a system of conclusions and concrete proposals aimed at strengthening and improving the financial sources, organizational, legal and financial framework of social protection, their theoretical justification.

The state employment policy in the regions is reflected in the development and implementation of national and regional employment programs based on the current situation in the labor market and its development prospects.

As a result of the ongoing reforms in the Republic in this area, the development of new forms of management is important in the conduct of effective public policy in the labor market. The emergence of new forms of management is carried out in accordance with the processes of diversification of the economy and the modernization of emerging industries.

The conditions necessary for the growth of self-employment are more in line with the conditions for the effective growth of a free market economy. In practice, the existence of self-employment depends on the private sector, so the political and economic conditions that promote the growth of the private sector also contribute to the development of self-employment.

One of the tasks of the second stage of economic reforms was to attract more people to small and private businesses, to form a layer of entrepreneurs and property owners in the country, and thus to provide employment. In order to provide employment for the population, the following tasks are envisaged in the development of the labor market; increase the implementation of measures aimed at increasing the demand for labor and reducing its supply; creation of a strong and fast-growing system of employment services and its infrastructure; formation of rational employment of the population; reducing unemployment to acceptable levels; improving the skills, competitiveness, social protection and exports of unemployed local employees, creating effective organizational, economic and legal mechanisms to regulate employment and unemployment in the labor market, etc.

During the years of development of the employment service, laws, requirements and socio-economic conditions are changing, and accordingly, detailed and clear adjustments are being made to changes in the activities. However, the formation and development of the organizational structure of the state employment service has remained virtually unchanged for many years.

CONCLUSION

To date, the analysis of the employment situation in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the analysis of the use of labor force in the study of the creation of new jobs in enterprises using surveillance methods (questionnaire surveillance,

monographic surveillance), small business and private entrepreneurship it is important to study issues such as assessment of the population as a key factor in employment.

In short, improving the welfare of the population in our country is a complex system of measures to develop living standards, create new jobs, develop small business and private entrepreneurship, support family business increase employment through support, employment and employment of graduates of professional colleges, support of individual entrepreneurship, provision of soft loans to entrepreneurs to start their own businesses, in fact to improve the mechanisms for identifying and targeting socially vulnerable groups, strengthening the legal framework and financial sources of social protection, establishing social partnerships between the state and citizens in society, improving the living standards of non-governmental organizations. tob including more engagement

REFERENCES

1. Soliyev, I. I. (2020). Methods for Selecting Innovative Projects for Implementation. International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies, 23(2), 263-266.
2. Солиев, И. И., & Сирожиддинов, К. (2020). ВОПРОСЫ ПОДДЕРЖАНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ АГРАРНЫХ ПРОИЗВОДИТЕЛЕЙ. Экономика и социум, (6-2),317-322.
3. Солиев, И. И., & Сирожиддинов, К. (2020). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ МАРКЕТИНГА ПЛОДООВОЩНОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ НА СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ. Экономика и социум, (6-2), 312-316.
4. Abduazizova, V. V., & Soliev, I. I. (2020). METHODS OF DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ABILITIES OF STUDENTS. Экономика и социум, (6), 3-6.
5. Солиев, И. И. (2020). ОСНОВНЫЕ ФАКТОРЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ. Экономика и социум, (4), 884-887.
6. Soliyev, I. (2020). Formation of innovative activities in the educational system: technological approach. Вестник педагогики: наука и практика, (51), 150-151.

7. Soliev, I. I. (2019). INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES IN THE ECONOMY AND THEIR PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE. Экономика и социум, (6), 68-69.
8. Ismatullaevich, S. I., & Yakubovich, Y. A. (2019). The role of innovative activity in the SocioEconomic development of society. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 9(4), 93-98.
9. Soliyev, I. I., & Shokirov, A. (2018). THE MAIN FEATURES OF INNOVATION RISKS. Теория и практика современной науки, (1), 773-775.
10. SOLIEV, I., & DADAMIRZAEV, M. (2017). Corporate governance as the way of investment attraction. Современные научные исследования и разработки, (4), 11-13.
11. Солиев, И. И. (2020). ОСНОВНЫЕ ФАКТОРЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ. Экономика и социум, (4), 884-887.
12. СОЛИЕВ, И., ЖУРАЕВ, Х., & СИРОЖИДДИНОВ, К. (2017). Особенности инновационной направленности экономического развития в условиях региона. Современные научные исследования и разработки, (4), 275-277.
13. Солиев, И. И., & Сирожиддинов, К. И. (2015). Благоприятный инвестиционный климат-важный фактор макроэкономического развития. Молодой ученый, (17), 461-463.
14. Sarfraz, M., Ran, J., & Soliev, I. (2014). Restructuring and Performance Evaluation of Chinese Local Government: Problem, Reason, and Options of Change. Journal of Management Policies and Practices, 2(1), 1-15.
15. Ran, J., Soliev, I., & Sarfraz, M. (2014). An Analysis on the “Going out Policy” of Chinese-founded Enterprises and Cross-culture Management.